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*ЭКСПЕРТ – ЭТО ЧЕЛОВЕК, КОТОРЫЙ
СОВЕРШИЛ ВСЕ ВОЗМОЖНЫЕ ОШИБКИ
В ОЧЕНЬ УЗКОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ.*

Нильс Бор

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ENSURING DISTANCE IN PHILOSOPHICAL EDUCATION

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F.A.Ibrokhimov — Senior Lecturer, CHDPU

ibrohimovf2209@gmail.com

Republic of Uzbekistan, Chirchik city

Abstract: Achieving high efficiency in the education system is the main and only effective solution not only to socio-national issues, but also to regional and global problems. This is determined by ensuring continuity and continuity in education and the preparation of high-quality, mature, qualified, healthy and independent-thinking personnel. The article analyzes the conditions of continuity and continuity in the teaching of philosophical disciplines in educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and reveals the importance of philosophical disciplines in the development of a person with specific examples.

Keywords: coherence, philosophical sciences, independent thinking skills, healthy worldview, cultural approach, thought, social person.

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring connectivity between these system elements is important for the development of a particular industry. In particular, in the field of education. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On Education» defines «Continuity and consistency of education» as a separate principle. [1] At the heart of the state educational standard, as in the education system of all countries, is the principle of continuity. In the «State Educational Standard of General Secondary

Education», approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 187 dated April 6, 2017, the continuity of general secondary education with other types and stages of education and the coherence of the content of education are defined as one of the main principles of the state educational standard of general secondary education. [2] Also, in the «State Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan. State Educational Standard of Higher Education. The Basic Rules (Uz DSt 3556:2021) also stipulate that «Curriculum plans and programs of undergraduate programs of higher education are developed on the basis of state educational standards of higher education and qualification requirements of undergraduate programs, ensuring coherence and continuity with general secondary and secondary specialized, professional education» [3].

In recent years, serious attention has been paid to reforming the education sector, radically improving the quality of personnel training, and in particular, implementing the experience of developed foreign countries into the system. Reforms in this regard are reflected in the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On measures to further improve the activities of secondary specialized and vocational educational institutions» dated March 14, 2017, «On measures to further develop the higher education system» dated April 20, 2017, «On measures to further improve the post-secondary education system» dated May 22, 2017, as well as in the Decrees «On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030» No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019, «On measures to effectively organize the activities of the Ministry of Preschool and School Education and organizations under its system» No. PF-79 dated May 26, 2023. If we pay attention, we can see that these regulatory and legal documents cover all types of continuing education systems.

As with all subjects, achieving full implementation of the principle of «Continuity and Consistency of Education» in the teaching of philosophical subjects is directly related to the methodology of teaching the subject.

Continuity of education is a system of relationships that ensures the interaction of the main tasks, content and methods of teaching and upbringing in order to create a single continuous educational process at all stages of a person's development. At each time interval of classes, the teacher solves specific tasks. The connection and continuity of these tasks create conditions for the transition of students from simple to more complex forms of knowledge, behavior and activity (so to speak, a healthy worldview), ensuring their consistent solution. Systematicity and consistency allow us to estimate the speed of mastering a particular educational material, its comparability and value, as well as the development of independent comparative thinking skills. KDushinsky believed that «only a truly rational system, arising from the essence of objects, gives us complete control over our knowledge.» [4] Consistency and systematicity in teaching allow us to resolve the conflict between the need

to form a system of knowledge, skills and competencies in subjects and the formation of a holistic conceptual view of the world. This is primarily due to the systematic construction of programs and textbooks, the effective development of inter-subject and interdisciplinary cooperation. provided upon its launch.

Today, as a result of reforms in the education system, the number and quality of educational institutions in our country is steadily increasing. If in 2018 there were 9,774 general secondary educational institutions operating in our country, today we can see that their number is 10,750, an increase of 976 compared to 2018. The number of non-state general educational organizations is 393. According to the data of the Stat.edu.uz website, currently 213 higher educational institutions operate in Uzbekistan, including 30 foreign universities, 67 non-state universities and 116 state universities. The level of coverage of young people with higher education has increased sharply. (Paragraph 7 of the «Uzbekistan – 2030» Strategy set the task of «Increasing the level of youth coverage by higher education to at least 50 percent.»)

Developing independent thinking skills and strengthening a healthy worldview in young people is one of the most important conditions for achieving a free and prosperous life and sustainable development. In recent years, significant work has been carried out to fundamentally reform the national education system, form a healthy worldview, develop independent thinking skills, and train personnel with a modern healthy worldview and independent, systematic and analytical thinking for the socio-economic life of our country. Ensuring the coherence and continuity of philosophical education on the basis of these reforms is noted as one of the main tasks. At the same time, a number of problems and shortcomings remain that prevent the formation of a respectful attitude to social values established in society, the development of independent thinking skills in students and youth studying in preschool, general secondary, vocational and higher education systems, and the healthy thinking of students. In particular, «the process of organizing education in the higher education system and the system for assessing the knowledge of students studying do not meet today's requirements;

The lack of a modern system for evaluating the performance, knowledge, and pedagogical skills of professors and teachers negatively affects the quality of education;

The fact that entrance test questions for higher education institutions do not allow for the determination of an applicant's logical thinking ability is causing problems in admitting talented young people to higher education institutions;

The lack of effective public control over the educational process in higher education institutions is causing many problems in this area, primarily corruption;

«higher education institutions have not become centers of dialogue for the exchange of innovative and technological ideas, and the necessary conditions

have not been created for professors, young scientists, and students to take the initiative in systematically studying and analyzing existing problems and shortcomings in relevant fields and making proposals for their solutions» [5];

the increasing volume and visibility of information available on the global Internet and social networks, which is being used by various ideological centers as a weapon in the «struggle for consciousness»;

Work on the development of independent thinking skills, primarily philosophical education and spiritual upbringing, is not being carried out systematically and coherently. The family, neighborhood, and other institutions of civil society are not sufficiently involved in these processes;

There is a certain gap in the mechanisms for implementing the established measures for spiritual education, which is precisely this factor that distances these measures from their main goal.

the lack of a comprehensive approach to the formation of ideological immunity to factors that negatively affect the spiritual education of students and young people, the instillation of a sense of loyalty to national values in each individual, and so on.

In addition, paragraph 56 of the Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education set the task of «developing basic spiritual and moral qualities of students appropriate to their age – loyalty to the Motherland, entrepreneurship, willpower, ideological immunity, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, innovative thinking, and hard work – based on the curricula and spiritual and educational plans of the secondary specialized vocational and higher education system.» We cannot say that all segments of the population are covered (participated) in the implementation of this task.

At this point, let's clarify the meaning of the concept of «ideological immunity». As is known, the word «immunity» (Latin: *immunitas* – freedom from something, liberation, deliverance) is used more in medicine and refers to the ability of the human body to fight various external influences. The National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan defines it as follows: «Immunity means the protection, resistance, and resistance of living beings to «foreign» factors that violate their integrity and biological uniqueness. «Foreign» factors include bacteria and their toxins, viruses, fungi, protozoa, transplanted organs and tissues, altered cells of the organism (for example, tumor cells), etc.

The concept of «ideological immunity», which refers to a person's ability to consciously fight against various alien ideas and their effects, is widely used in scientific discourse. Various alien ideas include spiritual, informational, ideological threats, manipulative strategic programs of hegemonic forces (for example, the «FFF» program, the «Overton Window» or the program of destruction), geopolitical actions in the form of «soft power», views promoted under the guise of religion, etc. Especially today, when globalization processes

are in full swing, the importance and necessity of this concept and the factor it represents for society are increasing.

In his answers to questions from a reporter for the newspaper «Fidokor», the first President Islam Karimov raised the issue of forming ideological immunity among young people and emphasized the socio-political essence of the concept of «ideological immunity»: «It is known that in order to prevent any disease, first of all, immunity against it is formed in the human body. We also need to establish a healthy attitude towards the Motherland, the sacred religion of our ancestors, so to speak, to strengthen their ideological immunity. Only then will neither the „call“ of ignorant fanaticism, nor ideas that reject morality and are completely alien to us, be able to exert their influence.» [6]

The time demands the balanced development of all spheres of social life in order to build and strengthen a legal democratic state and a just civil society based on free market relations. In paragraph 7, updated on the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On the Strategy of Uzbekistan — 2030» No. PF-158 dated September 11, 2023, the goals of «Expanding the coverage of higher education, improving the quality of training specialists with higher education» and in paragraph 38, «Ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society» are set, and the indicators for its implementation are «Together fight against ideological attacks on the basis of the national idea, strengthen family — school — neighborhood cooperation and ensure the continuity of spiritual education on this basis.» In addition, this strategy also sets out the tasks of introducing effective teaching methods into educational processes, improving the status of teaching staff, widely involving the private sector in the field to develop education, expanding the level of coverage of higher education, and improving the quality of training of specialists with higher education.

In order to improve the quality of education, it is necessary that the goals and objectives of each subject are fully understood by all subjects of the educational process. In particular, the content of philosophical subjects and the methods of their presentation should serve to develop independent thinking skills in students, to form a healthy worldview by teaching them systematic and analytical thinking. Therefore, philosophical education should be carried out in a logical sequence — in coherence.

The aspect of continuity of philosophical knowledge and independent, healthy thinking skills ensures that students understand the true essence of events in social life, form their spiritual and moral thinking, that is, it serves the function of forming elements of a healthy worldview that are formed throughout the entire educational period. The implementation of the continuity of the philosophical education system on the basis of ensuring the fulfillment of the tasks of each stage contributes to its effectiveness.

Currently, we can see that in our country's general education schools, 34 hours are allocated annually in grades 1–11 to the subject of education (ethics and morals), which is included in the philosophical disciplines.

In primary grades (grades 1–4), the «Education» subject teaches rules of conduct in public places, interaction with society and nature, ethics, aesthetics, and basic issues related to social philosophy in an understandable manner.

In the upper grades (grades 5–9), young people are taught the content and significance of moral categories, norms. Special attention is paid to the formation of a sense of aspiration for moral principles (humanity, patriotism, humanism, tolerance ...) in students, as well as socially important qualities. Attention is paid to the formation of skills to understand society and its social norms, refinement and spirituality, dignity and worth, universal human values, the essence of events in society, the formation of social consciousness and its various forms (economic, legal).

In grades 10–11, the main emphasis is on developing a sense of duty to family and society, the content of world religions, the idea of enlightenment against ignorance, the secret of a happy life, human qualities, will, the ability to comparatively analyze different actions, the importance of the family, and the skills of critically analyzing various ideological processes and understanding their true meaning.

our country, academic lyceums and vocational colleges used to teach a philosophical subject called «Society and Personality.» Today, in academic lyceums, first-year students are taught the subject of education, while in technical schools, special emphasis is placed only on specialized subjects.

In the higher education system, in the direction of the National Idea, Fundamentals of Spirituality and Law, philosophical subjects such as «General Theoretical Issues of Philosophy», «Philosophy (Ethics, Aesthetics, Logic)», «Social Philosophy» and «Philosophy of Ideas», «Philosophy of Values» have been taught. For other educational areas, the subject «Philosophy» is taught for one semester. With the reforms in education, approaches to allocating more hours to specialized subjects in the curricula of educational areas, and the transition to the credit-module system, the hours allocated to the subject «Philosophy» in non-specialized educational areas have been reduced to a certain extent. In particular, this year, 4 credits (120 hours) were given to the subject «Philosophy» at the National University of Uzbekistan, 48 hours of which were allocated to classroom and 72 hours to independent study. At Chirchik State Pedagogical University, 4 credits (120 hours) are allocated to the subject «Philosophy», 60 hours of which are allocated to classroom and 60 hours to independent study).

Based on the principle of granting academic freedom to higher education institutions and the need-based approach to the development of educational

University	Science name							
	Philosophy	Logic (t)	Ethics. Aesthetics(t)	Social philosophy	Management ethics(t)	Human philosophy(t)	Axiology (t)	Philosophy of Law (t)
National University of Uzbekistan	2 s	-	3s	4s	5s	-	6s	-
CHDPU	2 s	3 s	4 s	5 s	6 s	6 s	8 s	8 s
All subjects are allocated 4 credits (120/60/60)								

s – semester symbol
t – symbol of the chosen subject

Route name	Science name									
	Philosophy	Logic (t)	Ethics. Aesthetics (t)	Social philosophy	Management ethics (t)	Human philosophy	Axiology (t)	Philosophy of Law (t)	Professional ethics	Informationization of society and ideological immunity (t)
National idea, foundations of spirituality and legal education	2 s	3 s	4 s	5 s	6 s	7 s	8 s	8 s	8 s	7 s
All subjects are allocated 4 credits (120/60/60)										

s – semester symbol
t – symbol of the chosen subject

and regulatory documents for educational areas, minor differences in the composition of philosophical disciplines and the volume of training in the direction of National Idea, Fundamentals of Spirituality and Legal Education appeared. Below is a comparative analysis of the curriculum of the direction of National Idea, Fundamentals of Spirituality and Legal Education approved in 2023 at the National University of Uzbekistan and Chirchik State Pedagogical University:

Starting from the current academic year, the curriculum for the National Idea, Fundamentals of Spirituality and Legal Education has been developed on a collaborative basis, and the same type and volume of compulsory subjects will

be taught throughout the republic. In particular, the following philosophical subjects will be taught in accordance with the curriculum approved in 2024 for the National Idea, Fundamentals of Spirituality and Legal Education at Chirchik State Pedagogical University:

Let us analyze the current state of continuity within the framework of the direction of national idea, spirituality and legal education. In this direction of education, the subjects of philosophy, social philosophy, professional ethics listed in the table above are currently taught as compulsory subjects, and the rest are taught as elective subjects. In order for the information within these subjects to be taught in a coherent manner within the framework of the established requirements, more emphasis is placed on the analytical explanation of science programs with life issues and the formation of independent thinking skills. However, ensuring continuity in philosophical subjects is largely related to the richness of the methodological base of the subject teacher, and there are also cases of repetition of materials from the lower education level in the lessons of young, inexperienced teachers.

«Continuity is understood as continuity across the boundaries of different stages and forms of education. Ultimately, this implies the unified organization of these stages or forms within a holistic system of education.» [7] The principle of continuity is taken into account in the selection of topics for educational subjects in the lower education system in undergraduate education, but there are certain differences in its full implementation in practice.

There are a number of factors that negatively affect the quality of education and the principle of continuity:

- shortage of teaching staff in some central regions (mainly in the school education system, in the case of Tashkent);

- the current state of the teacher training system in its traditional form (one of the latest reforms, namely the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 415 dated July 11, 2024 «On measures to effectively organize the system of retraining and advanced training of managerial and pedagogical personnel of higher education institutions», removed the obligation to take a master class in the specialty from students who completed an alternative form of advanced training. In our opinion, on the contrary, increasing the number of master classes will serve to exchange methods among advanced training students and enrich teaching methodologies);

- teachers lack the necessary skills to convey to the audience how necessary knowledge of this subject is (first of all, the student must deeply understand how necessary this topic is for him/her at the beginning of each lesson);

- parents do not see themselves as subjects of education, the insufficient formation of the institution of public control, and the low activity of public associations in this area (low level of cooperation between educational entities);

- the lack of sufficient initiative on the part of employees of educational management organizations (ministries of education and their subordinates), as well as their indifference to the provision of methodological resources;
- factors related to the goals and objectives of the lesson (the determination of the true goal of each stage and topic and specific tasks leading to this goal, as well as the presence of factors that prevent the full implementation of these tasks, as in various fields, the primary focus on official documents, resulting in inadequate achievement of the main educational-educational-developmental goal);
- factors related to educational technologies (widespread use of traditional teaching methods and tools, if I may say so, the priority of only traditional methods, that is, not conducting lessons in the form of excursions, direct demonstration processes (for example, visiting museums, theaters, organizing interviews with people with extensive life experience);
- planned events (lack of information about certain parts of the lesson due to various events at the educational institution being held during the school day);
- the lack of the required level of skills for working together in educational subjects (in some foreign educational institutions, when performing a given task, several students work together, each studying the shared part of the task based on their own abilities and teaching each other the rest; our educational subjects lack precisely such skills), etc.

CONCLUSION

From the analysis of the studied cases, we can conclude that we cannot say that the continuity of teaching philosophical subjects in the education system is fully ensured. We believe that in order to achieve effective results in the system of teaching philosophical subjects, it is necessary to first eliminate the above shortcomings, and at the same time ensure mutual cooperation between all educational branches in order to further improve the quality of education and the potential of future personnel. After all, as the head of our state Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized, «Improving the quality of education is the only correct way for the development of New Uzbekistan.»

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